

DUTIES OF PARENTS IN FORMING SPIRITUAL EDUCATION IN THE FAMILY.

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Annotation: This article is about the unique national characteristics of the Uzbek family and the relations between family members, parental responsibility and children's relations, moral values, and spiritual upbringing in the family. The role of parents in its formation is highlighted.

Keywords: family education, parents, spirituality, child, values, universal, moral, perfect, perfect person, historicity, succession, duty

Introduction: It is known that the Uzbek family has its characteristics. Nationality is reflected in the relations between Uzbek family members. Traditions inherited from time immemorial is the basis of family education. Education is given to children by parents, and it is based on ancient values. The more educated a parent is, the better he can educate a child.

The main part: The uniqueness of family upbringing, its essence, traditionality, its importance in the system of national and universal moral values, its integral connection with them, interaction, the role of the family environment in raising a perfect generation and a perfect person is classical. and the present time occupies an important place in the development of philosophical thinking.

There were very important and instructive thoughts on this issue in world philosophy. It is worth noting that the common memory of the Turkic people is "Avesta", "O'rhunEnasoy writings", as well as Plato, Aristotle, Confucius, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Yusuf Khos Hajib, and the philosophers of the present time expressed their unique opinions. In the scientific-theoretical works of thinkers such as Kaikovus, Nizami Aruzi, Abu-Lays Samarkand, Sa'diy Sherozi, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Avloni, education in 6 family relations is described from the point of view of historicity and succession. The great philosophers of our republic in their scientific works have touched on the influence of nationalism and universality on the educational process, family, and spirituality issues in their scientific works. The problems of the family in raising children, and the issues of education and training in it, have attracted the attention of people of science and creativity since time immemorial.[1]

What constitutes the economic, legal, spiritual, and natural foundations of family life and life? The question of how family education is based on the laws has been

a relevant issue in all periods of human history. It is necessary to think separately about the advanced ideas of the ancient culture of our nation and people of 3000 years ago and the rich spiritual teaching, good thoughts, good words, and good deeds of the written monument "Avesta" will come. "This is a rare book," said I. Karimov in a conversation with historians, "it is a spiritual and historical heritage left to our descendants by our ancestors who lived on this land between two rivers in the 20th century ago." "Avesta" is a historical document testifying to the existence of a great state, a great spiritual horse, and a great culture in this ancient country, which no one can deny." [1]

Parents should convey to their children that proper organization of children's life in family upbringing is the main guarantee of correct and productive use of their time. Abu Ali Ibn Sina wrote a special workshop entitled "Tadbir al-manzil" on issues of family education. In it, the scientist highlighted the duties of parents in raising a child. The work focuses on the duties and responsibilities of parents, family relations, and especially the hard work of parents in the family 9, and the importance of training their children in professions and trades. In Ibn Sina's educational views, family and family matters are given a wide place. In the family, a father should set an example for his children in every way: correctness and truthfulness, sincerity in behavior, manners of speech, the culture of speech, the process of interaction, and most importantly practical work. The scientist believed that the main means of the correct upbringing of a child in the family is the formation of faith in his spiritual world. [2]

In our republic, where "family relations are the highest value", the social status of the family is extremely high, and it maintains its status until now. In the Uzbek family, the necessary educational factor and skills are passed from generation to generation. The maintenance of patriarchal order in Uzbek families with many children ensured the stability of family relations. However, today the family crisis affects many families, including Uzbek families. Due to the decrease in the number of family members and the increase in the problem of the separation of generations, the issue of forming family relations is becoming more and more important. Today, the family needs the help of highly qualified psychologists and social pedagogues. Family is an integral part of society. There is no nation, nation, or society that has not taken into account the problems and values of the family and its surroundings in the history of its development and in determining the prospects for development. Any perspective cannot be imagined apart from the interests of the family. After all, family is the beginning of life for everyone, the prelude to everything. In addition, every person connects his happiness and

happiness first of all with his family, that is, only a person who is happy in his home and family feels completely happy.[3]

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